

Interaction of Chlorosulphonic Acid with the Substituted Amides of Malonic and Methylmalonic Acids.

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The investigation which forms the subject of this communication was undertaken with a view to study the reactivity of the two hydrogen atoms of a reactive methylene group situated between two carbonyl groups, $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$, as in the case of the substituted amides of malonic acid. Reference is invited to a previous communication by Naik and Amin (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 579). Attention is here confined to the study of the interaction of some of the substituted amides of malonic acid using chlorosulphonic acid as the reagent. For this purpose the interaction of chlorosulphonic acid with the following substances was studied:—

(1) Malon-diphenylamide, (2) Malon-dibenzylamide, (3) Malon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (4) Malon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (5) Malon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (6) Malon-di- α -naphthylamide, (7) Malon-di- β -naphthylamide, (8) Malon-di-(1:3:4)-xylylide, (9) Malon-dipropylamide, (10) Malon-mono-*p*-tolylamide, (11) Methylmalon-diphenylamide, (12) Methylmalon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (13) Methylmalon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (14) Methylmalon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (15) Methylmalon-di- α -naphthylamide, (16) Methylmalon-di- β -naphthylamide, (17) Methylmalon-di-(1:3:4)-xylylide.

Of the above, compounds, 8, 15, 16 and 17 were prepared for the first time, by the same method as that used for preparing the corresponding amides of malonic acid.

The results of the present investigation could be summarised as under:—

Type I. Compounds (1) to (10), with the exception of (9), react to form disulpho-compounds whose constitution can be generally represented as:—

(R = phenyl, benzyl, tolyl, naphthyl, or xylyl group.)

Type II. Compounds (11) to (17) give rise to disulpho-derivatives, which can generally be represented as:—

Compound (9) reacts with chlorosulphonic acid to form a derivative which can be represented as:—

That the constitution assigned to (I, R = Ph) is correct and that all the sulpho-acids, derived from the various amides enumerated above, can generally be thus represented, follows from the following considerations:—

(i) That the hydrogen atoms attacked by the chlorosulphonic acid are not eliminated from the phenyl groups or any such analogous nucleus becomes evident from the course of the reaction in the case of malon-dipropylamide where no such aromatic nuclei are present, and yet the sulpho-acid is produced.

(ii) That the hydrogen atoms eliminated were not those which were originally attached to the two nitrogen atoms, because only one sulpho-group enters in malon-dipropylamide, though there are two symmetrically situated —NH— groups present in it.

The compounds enumerated under type (I) reacted similarly with chlorosulphonic acid. Only in the case of malon-di-*a*-naphthylamide, a longer time was required before the reaction was complete.

In the above cases, molecular proportions of the reacting substances did not give a good yield of the sulpho-acids and much of the amide remained unaltered. When they were taken in equal quantities, the yield improved and the products were obtained in a purer state.

With a view to study the stability of the two sulphonic acid groups, attached to the methylene carbon atom, it was thought desirable to see how far these groups could be replaced by a negative group, such as the nitro-group.

The following four compounds were, therefore, subjected to a process of nitration:—

- (1) Disulpho-malon-diphenylamide;
- (2) Disulpho-malon-di-*p*-tolylamide;
- (3) Disulpho-malon-di-*o*-tolylamide;
- (4) Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-diphenylamide.

Compounds (2) and (3) when treated with dilute nitric acid yielded dinitro-derivatives, thus:—

Compounds (1) and (4) on being nitrated gave tetranitro-derivatives. Thus in the case of (1) the reaction followed the course as under:—

The tetranitro-derivative obtained from disulpho-malon-diphenylamide was hydrolysed with 50 per cent. aqueous caustic potash solution, thus:—

The formation of potassium dinitro-malonate as above shows that the two $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups originally present in the disulpho-amide, were replaced by the nitro-groups, the other two being present in the aromatic nuclei of the above amide. Both the sulpho-groups seem to have been simultaneously replaced by the two nitro-groups.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A general method of preparing the sulpho-acids is to add equal quantities of the amide and chlorosulphonic acid to dry chloroform in a conical flask. When properly mixed the reaction starts and proceeds vigorously with much evolution of heat. Clouds of hydrogen chloride are thrown out in the initial stage of the reaction. The flask is kept normally cool by holding under a water-tap. Subsequently, the mixture is refluxed on a sand-bath for two hours, when

the evolution of hydrogen chloride stops. The solvent is then removed and the red syrupy reaction product poured into 100 c.c. of water. The syrupy mass goes into solution. On concentration and cooling, the sulpho-acid separates out in clusters of shining leaflets.

Disulpho-malon-diphenylamide.—It was obtained from malondi-phenylamide (3 g.) and chlorosulphonic acid (3 g.) in 20 c.c. of chloroform. It formed shining colourless leaflets, soluble in water, and insoluble in alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, benzene, toluene, carbon disulphide, carbon tetrachloride, ether, ethyl acetate, nitrobenzene and light petroleum. It has no definite m.p. but decomposes above 280°. It crystallises out with two molecules of water of crystallisation, which is lost when heated to 140–150° for four hours. (Found: S, 14·3; H₂O, 7·6; Equiv. wt., 224. C₁₅H₁₄O₈N₂S₂, 2H₂O requires S, 14·2; H₂O, 8·0 per cent. Equiv. wt., 225).

Nitration.—The above disulpho-acid (2 g.) was gradually added to a mixture of 20 c.c. of nitric acid (*d* 1·2) and 20 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. On warming the mixture, oxides of nitrogen began to evolve. The reaction mixture was kept on a water-bath till the evolution of the fumes ceased. Then the remaining fumes of nitrogen peroxide were blown away by air and the mixture poured into water. On concentration, the nitro-compound crystallised out in the form of deep orange crystals, m. p. 124°. The product was found to be soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform, acetone and nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 19·32. C₁₅H₁₀O₁₀N₆ requires N, 19·35 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of Dinitromalon-dinitrodiphenylamide.—About 2 g. of the substance were refluxed for several hours with 50 per cent. caustic potash solution and the resulting solution was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on the water-bath, when potassium dinitromalonate separated out, which was collected, and recrystallised from hot water. (Found: K, 29·02. C₃O₈N₂K₂ requires K, 28·88 per cent.).

The *barium salt*, Ba(SO₃)₂:C:(CO·NHC₆H₅)₂·H₂O, was prepared by digesting an aqueous solution of the acid with barium carbonate. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on being concentrated deposited the barium salt as needle-shaped crystals. (Found: H₂O, 3·09; Ba, 24·41. C₁₅H₁₂O₈N₂S₂Ba·H₂O requires H₂O, 3·17; Ba, 24·2 per cent.).

The *potassium salt*, (KSO₃)₂:C:(CO·NHC₆H₅)₂·9H₂O, was prepared by the action of caustic potash on the solution of the acid.

(Found: H_2O , 24.46; K, 11.94. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{K}_2, 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 24.85; K, 11.96 per cent.).

The *sodium salt*, $(\text{NaSO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{C} : (\text{CO} \cdot \text{NHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared in a similar way using caustic soda. (Found: H_2O , 10.39; Na, 9.01. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Na}_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 10.54; Na, 8.98 per cent.).

Calcium salt.—It was prepared like the barium salt, and crystallised from alcohol. (Found: Ca, 8.5. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Ca}, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ca, 8.51 per cent.).

Ammonium salt.—The solution of the acid was just neutralised with ammonium hydroxide and concentrated when it crystallised out in large prisms. (Found: H_2O , 8.84; N, 12.06. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 8.86; N, 12.01 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-dibenzylamide.—Two g. of the amide were made to react with 2 g. of the acid in 20 c.c. of chloroform. The reaction product was obtained by a process similar to that followed in the preparation of disulphomalon-diphenylamide. The pure substance was crystallised from distilled water. It had no definite melting point, but decomposed at temperatures above 300° . (Found: H_2O , 3.98; S, 14.08. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 3.61; S, 13.9 per cent.).

The *barium salt*, $\text{Ba}(\text{SO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{C} : (\text{CO} \cdot \text{NHC}_7\text{H}_7)_2, \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared as usual by neutralising the sulpho-acid with barium carbonate. (Found: H_2O , 1.54; Ba, 23.43. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Ba}, \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 1.53; Ba, 23.42 per cent.).

Sodium salt.—It was prepared as usual. (Found: Na, 9.44. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Na}_2$ requires Na, 9.46 per cent.).

Potassium salt.—(Found: K, 15.12. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{K}_2$ requires K, 15.05 per cent.).

The *ammonium salt*, $(\text{NH}_4\text{SO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{C} : (\text{CO} \cdot \text{NHC}_7\text{H}_7)_2, \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared by neutralisation of the acid with ammonium hydroxide. (Found: H_2O , 1.46; N, 11.31. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}_2, \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 1.82; N, 11.33 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-p-tolylamide.—The amide (3 g.) was made to react with chlorosulphonic acid (3 g.) in 25 c.c. of dry chloroform. The product (which was obtained by the method adopted in the previous cases) was found to be insoluble in all organic solvents. It was soluble only in hot water and had no definite melting point but decomposed at 300° . (Found: S, 14.42. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires S, 14.47 per cent.).

Hydrolysis.—The above acid (5 g.), was added to a solution of 30 g. of caustic soda in 100 c.c. of alcohol and the whole refluxed for 48 hours. The resulting product was diluted with water and then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract deposited *p*-toluidine after removal of ether.

Nitration.—The acid (1 g.) was added to 20 c.c. of dilute nitric acid. On heating and concentrating the solution, the reaction product was obtained as orange crystals very soluble in alcohol, benzene, acetone and acetic acid but sparingly so in petroleum. It melts at 68°. (Found: N, 14.08. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-o-tolylamide.—Two g. of the amide and 3 g. of chlorosulphonic acid were used. On crystallisation from water the product formed long, silky needles. (Found: S, 14.5. $C_{17}H_{18}O_8N_2S_2$ requires S, 14.47 per cent.).

Potassium salt.—(Found: K, 15.06. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_2S_2K_2$ requires K, 15.05 per cent.).

Nitration.—The acid, on nitration, as in the case of the *para*-derivative, gave a greenish coloured product, m.p. 85°. (Found: N, 15.1. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.05 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-m-tolylamide.—Two g. of the amide and 2 g. of the acid in 20 c.c. of chloroform were taken. The product was obtained from water in white plates. (Found: S, 13.9; H_2O , 3.98. $C_{17}H_{18}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires S, 13.9; H_2O , 3.91 per cent.).

The *calcium salt* was prepared as usual. (Found: Ca, 8.47. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_2S_2Ca$ requires Ca, 8.3 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-a-naphthylamide.—This was prepared by allowing 3 g. of the amide to react with 10 g. of the acid in 30 c.c. of chloroform. The product was found to be soluble only in water. (Found: H_2O , 12.92; S, 11.01. $C_{23}H_{19}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires H_2O , 12.2; S, 10.92 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-β-naphthylamide.—Two g. of the amide were treated with 10 g. of chlorosulphonic acid. The disulpho-derivative was found to be very sparingly soluble in water. It had no definite melting point but decomposed at 280°. (Found: H_2O , 17.4; S, 10.32. $C_{23}H_{18}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires H_2O , 17.36; S, 10.28 per cent.).

Monosulphomalon-dipropylamide.—Two g. of the amide were made to react with 2 g. of the acid. The product could not be isolated in crystalline form, but was obtained as a red syrup. It was

soluble in all organic solvents. Its *barium salt* was obtained in the form of large shining leaflets from water. (Found: H_2O , 7.5; Ba, 19.08. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Ba}, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 7.4; Ba, 19.00 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-mono-p-tolylamide.—This was prepared by treating the mono-amide (2 g.) with chlorosulphonic acid (2 g.) in the usual manner. It was crystallised from water in short needles. (Found: H_2O , 4.93; S, 17.27. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 4.8; S, 17.29 per cent.).

Disulphomalon-di-(1:3:4)xylylide.—The product from 2 g. of the xylylide and 2 g. of the sulphonic acid separated as white lustrous laminae from hot water. (Found: S, 13.62. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires S, 13.61 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-diphenylamide.—It was prepared by the interaction of 2 g. of the amide and 2 g. of the acid. It comes out from water in white crystals. (Found: S, 14.94. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires S, 14.95 per cent.).

Nitration.—The acid was gradually added to a mixture of 20 c.c. of nitric acid (d 1.2) and 20 c.c. of acetic acid. After the evolution of the oxides of nitrogen had ceased, it was poured in a small quantity of water, when the nitrated product came out as yellow crystals, m.p. 120° . (Found: N, 18.78. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_6$ requires N, 18.75 per cent.).

Potassium salt.—(Found: K, 14.97. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{K}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires K, 14.94 per cent.).

Sodium salt.—(Found: Na, 9.71. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{Na}_2$ requires Na, 9.74 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di-p-tolylamide.—It was obtained in the form of shining needles from hot water. (Found: H_2O , 8.9; S, 13.56. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 8.8; S, 13.5 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di-o-tolylamide.—It was obtained from water in white shining crystals, by a process similar to the above. (Found: H_2O , 3.92; S, 13.6. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 3.8; S, 13.5 per cent.).

Potassium salt.—(Found: H_2O , 6.4; K, 13.71. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{K}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 6.38; K, 13.73 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di-m-tolylamide was prepared in the usual way, from methylmalon-di-m-tolylamide. (Found: S, 14.12. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires S, 14.08 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di- α -naphthylamide.—It was obtained from 2 g. of the amide and 10 g. of chlorosulphonic acid. (Found: H_2O , 14.54; S, 10.37. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot 5H_2O$ requires H_2O , 14.56; S, 10.36 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di- β -naphthylamide was obtained in a similar way. (Found: H_2O , 9.4; S, 11.01. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2S_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires H_2O , 9.28; S, 10.99 per cent.).

Sulphomethyl-sulphomalon-di-(1:3:4)xylylide was obtained in the form of white scales. (Found: S, 13.24. $C_{20}H_{24}O_8N_2S_2$ requires S, 13.22 per cent.).

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